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642. Egyptian arabic

lit.: Olmstedt, Judith and Gary, Saad Gamal ad-Din: Cairene Egyptian Colloquial Arabic (1982)

Mitchell T.F. : An introduction to Egyptian Colloquial Arabic (1956)

Hayes, Bruce: Metrical stress theory (1995)

I. Segmental Properties

- The domain explicitly mentioned by the author for all described stuff is the phonological word
- /q/ and /Ō/ only in loanwords borrowed from classical arabic and european languages
- /g/ followed by /u:/ very limited occurrence
- any consonant may occur in word final position when that position is filled by a single consonant
- maximum of two consonants can occur word finally but no geminates, there are exceptions see Olmstedt & Gary p.122:
 - ☐ all medially non-occurring clusters do not occur finally
 - ☐ following combinations do not occur finally:
bh hg bj dj gw gj zw zj ʔw wb wd wg wʔ wʔ jb jd jg jz jʔ jʔ ʔk xk xh ʔh nw jw
- there are no restriction on initial consonants
- no word initial consonant clusters
 - ☐ consonant clusters over morpheme boundary word- internally: (Olmstedt) ?
it-tajjaar-a
the-plane-Fem.sg
ʔiddit-lu-hum 'she gave to them'
 - ☐ no affixes with consonant clusters in the beginning
- maximum of two consonant clusters may occur word medially:
 - if they are not identical: first closes the preceding syllable, second releases the following ; e.g. êar-du
 - if they are identical: gemination with consonant articulation held over syllable boundary ; e.g. êarru
- consonant clusters which aren't allowed to occur medially aren't allowed to occur medially besides others
- vowels /a, i, u/ only allowed for word finally
- no word initial vowels except in morphophonemic alternations as:
word initial syllable CVC and initial C is glottal stop and the vowel is under weak stress then the vowel may devoice and the syllable alternate to 'VC
this process is restricted to /i/
- sequences of syllabic vowels don't occur
 - ☐ in (Olmstedt) the notion of the non-occurrence of syllabic vowels is not further explained nor are there examples
 - ☐ but also in (Mitchell) : no syllable without consonant in the beginning
 - ☐ therefore V.V should be forbidden
 - ☐ syllable types (Mitchell): CV ; CVV ; CVC ; CVVC ; CVCC
 - ☐ every syllable must begin with a consonant
- restriction, when C in pre-pausal position in a sequence VC is filled with by semi-

vowels: only /a/ or /a:/ csn occur

- vowel allophony is conditioned by vowel quality across morpheme boundary, but this phenomenon isn't universal
 - ☐ ex. (Olmstedt): faʔr 'poverty': front allophone [Q] when adjective formant –i is suffixed [fQʔri] 'poorish' faʔr
 - 'honor' [fQʔri] 'honorary' but no universal phenomenon
 - ☐ ex. Sart 'condition' but Sarti - same back vowel allophone
 - ☐ no total assimilation, feature of frontness
- emphasis spreads over syllable: e.g. édarb > édaéréb (back allophone of /a/)
- regressive assimilation occurs when two segments usually divided by internal juncture in careful speech are brought into close transition in rapid speech thereby constituting one phonological word
 - e.g. saêaat kitira > saêaakkitira ,many watches'
- lengthening of short vowels: sequences stressed on the penult and ending with a short vowel lengthen the vowel when followed in close transition by a sequence C(V) or CVC an dstress shifts over to the lengthend vowel
 - e.g. éédarába > édarabná:kum
- shortening of long vowels by combination with suffix
- only vowels in weak stressed position within the foot undergo a rule phrasal syncope
- domain: two prosodic words – between them interaction : syllable shifting
 - first word ends with an open syllable
 - second drops its first vowel, the first consonant shifts back to the first word closes the last syllable of the first word
 - occurs only in rapid speech
- when /il ,the" or /it ,passive verb formant' is prefixed to a root the –l or –t is assimilated into the first consonant of the following root, if the consonant is dental, velar or palatal very productive, also for loanwords
- words ending in a vowel and incorporating a suffix break vowel **sequence with semi-vowel**
 - e.g. li + i > lijja
 - for 1.sg.poss for me
- minimal segmental sequence of CV under major stress (primary or secondary) and is flanked by pause
 - ☐ the question of minimal word is not explicitly answered, CV is the minimal syllable
 - ☐ in the glossary there are few words of CV: wa ~ wi 'and'; fi 'in'; da 'that (demonstrative)'; bi 'with'; li 'to'
 - ☐ but they don't seem to be phonological words on their own, because the author (Olmstedt) calls them "bound prepositions" bi – fi – li they combine with the article to form phonological words
 - ☐ ex.: huwwa fi-l beet 'he is in the house'
 - la-ha 'to her'
 - ☐ pronominal suffixes which follow prepositions assume the same form as when they are suffixed to a nominal, confirming to the same phonological rules
 - ex.: ?il-walad wi-l-banaat 'the boy and the girls'
- polysyllabic words may consist of more than one morpheme

- lexical morphemes may or may not coincide with word boundaries
- syllables fall into three categories: light CV, heavy CVC or CV:, superheavy CVCC or CV:C
 - ☐ examples for monosyllabic words:
 - ☐ CVCC: ?ibn ‘son’; bint ‘daughter’; kirS ‘belly’
 - ☐ CVVC: Xaal ‘uncle’; joom ‘day’; gooz ‘husband’, leel ‘night’
- the superheavy syllables are largely restricted to final position

II. Prosodic Properties

- one primary stress per word
- syllables under non-primary stress vary non-distinctively in their stress degree, free variation
- difference between stress in Cairene Classical Arabic and in colloquial is that words with final long vowels are said to receive non-final stress in Cairene Classical but final stress in the colloquial
- pattern rules (McCarthy):
 - stress the final if it is superheavy or colloquial CV:
 - e.g. katábt , I wrote’, gató: ,cake’ (loanword)
 - otherwise stress the penult if it is heavy
 - e.g. bé:tak ,your house’
 - otherwise stress the penult or antepenult whichever is separated by an even number of syllables from the closest preceding heavy syllable or if there’s no such syllable from the beginning of the word
 - e.g. qattála ,he killed’ (penult, counted from heavy syllable)
(heavy – light – light)
 - kátaba ,he wrote’ (antepenult, counted from beginning)

proposed simplification by Hayes:

- important is syllable quantity
- in non-final position weight distinction is ordinary, opposing light CV syllables to heavier syllables
- in final position is the opposition binary but on a different basis: syllable types CV:C, CVCC, CV: attract stress while CVC and CV do not
- Hayes’ analysis as a case of consonant extrametricality demotes heavy CVC to light CV<C> in final position while retaining final CV:, CVC<C>, CV:<C> as heavy
- In classical egyptian arabic final CV: are counted as light
- Additional rule: marking of the second mora of a long vowel as extrametrical in classical words
- Feet are defined as moraic trochee
- Foot consists of two moras of which the first is stronger
- Parse the word from left to right
- Heavy syllables are necessarily followed by foot boundaries
- Single light syllable cannot form a foot
- Allows syllables which are not footed
- Metrical structures that generate primary stress also predict secondary stresses on the heads of non-primary stressed feet
- Stress is determined by syllable-structure of words, irrespective of morphological boundaries

III: Morpho-Syntax

- non-adjacent allomorphy ? : imperative expressed by prefix to indicativ imperfect stem triggers special suffixed forms in 2.sg, pl.
e.g. katabt ,you (masc.) wrote' ; 'iktibi ,write! (you, masc.)'
- concatenative morphology by affixes (e.g. cross-reference in verbs: person, number)
 - mostly non-linear morphology: various vocalism indicating tense, mood, voice are superimposed on a consonantal sceleton
- circumfixation: sentential negation: ma-verb- Δ
precedes and follows all other prefixes and suffixes
- partial reduplication of second consonant of triconsonantal verb root makes an intransitive verb transitive, also used for causativation and as a intensive or iterative formant
e.g. mawat ,die' > mawwit ,cause to die'
- complete reduplication: one syllable CVC reduplicated
in verb formation nmay exist the monsyllabic origin, the vowel of the now secon syllable may be different
but in noun formation mostly there doesn't exist the monosyllabic base, only the reduplicated result
e.g. filfil ,pepper' , ,fil' doesn't exist
- restrictions on verbs and nouns formed by reduplication:
 - all such formations are bisyllabic
 - no long vowels
 - in verb formation where the vowel of the second syllable is different from the vowel of the first syllable the sequence is /a/, /i/
 - no reduplicated verb forms with /r/, /d/, /j/
 - if first consonant of reduplicated syllable is glottal stop, vowel must be /a/
 - but no further information or examples
- clitic: little information
negation clitic mi Δ occurs before verb forms or non-finite forms, before nouns, pronouns, adjectives and prepositions
it has no allomorphs
connective ,wi' - can occur in initial position in discourse
some prepositions
- particle: also little information
no particle can occur sentence finally or initially unless it is combined with a nominal or verbal form
negation particle bala: Δ occurs before imperfect form of verb
vocative particle is obligatory when the vocative modifier is a noun and at the end of the phrase and the particle is optional, if the nouns occurs at the beginning of the phrase

IV. Other Questions

- weak stress on the devoiced vowel between consonants reduces vowel length, such that it may result in a consonant cluster
- in CV'CV(V)C any of the short vowels could occur in the first syllable, however only /i/ and /u/ could be shortened and devoiced this is not predictabel in terms of consonantial environment but conditioned by syllabic and stress distribution

- very few compound patterns except preposition compound
 - ☐ there is a wordlist but without compounds
 - ☐ the noun/noun constructions are status-constructus-constructions

ex.: geeb saaʒa	saaʒit geeb
pocket watch	watch pocket
a watch pocket	a pocket watch
- usually noun/noun combination (no examples or details)
- process of compounding seems not to be very productive
- word-word-combinations: two lexical verbs may string together with constraints:
 - first member must belong to a limited group of motion verbs
 - the two verbs must agree in the subject pronoun marker in person/number/gender
 - if first is in imperative, second must be imperative too
 - if first is in indicative perfect, second is in indicative perfect or imperfect
 - if first is in indicative imperfect, second must be imperfect too
 e.g. ru: ʔ Suʔ ʔAXuʔk, Go see your brother<#
 !!! but elements can be interposed: ru ʔ ʒaSaʔn tiSuʔ ʔAXuʔk
 go.you in order to-see.you brother-your

- periphrastic morphology: form of ka:n, 'was' + infinitive perfect or imperfect form of the verb

express relative tense : * past-in-the past: perfect of ka:n + perfect of verb

e.g. ka:n xarag, 'he had gone'

* future-in-the-past: perfect of ka:n + future of verb

e.g. kunt ha-fu:t, 'I was going to come'

* past-in-the future: imperfect form jiku:n + verb in perfect

e.g. 'aku:n xallast, 'I'll have finished'

- some prepositions share membership with other word classes
- prepositions: the complement can be either a noun or a pronoun
 - e.g. bi-l 'alam, 'with the pencil'; maêaa-h, 'with him'
- bound preposition followed by a personal pronoun result in some morphological change; e.g. bi, 'with' + -i, '1.sg' > bijja
- pronouns have the same form as in post-nominal position
- bound prepositions combine with article ʔil and form phonological words in certain phonological changes
- some prepositions can occur either with or without complements
- prepositions cannot be stranded if their noun phrase is moved unless a pronoun trace is left behind
- combination of two locational prepositions make up a prepositional phrase
 - e.g. min foʔ, 'from above'